

**Inscription of Periodical Surface Structures in
Photopolymer Material by Multiple Beam
Holographic Recording**

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Declaration of Integrity

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Abstract

A method for producing square and rectangular photonic crystal lattices using a 3-beam holographic set-up was devised. The efficacy of the method was tested using computer simulations and by recording the lattices onto an acrylamide-based photopolymer material. The simulation was used to analyse the theoretical spatial variation of intensity of the interference pattern resulting from the interference of the 3 beams. Two of the five two-dimensional Bravais lattices, square and rectangular, were recorded onto the photopolymer. The structure of the recordings was analysed post recording by probing the gratings with a reference wave and measuring the diffraction efficiency in each diffraction order. Images of the structures were taken using a microscope and the lattice constants were measured and compared with the results of the simulation. The spatial Fourier transforms of the images were taken using the ImageJ image processing software. The reciprocal lattice vectors were measured and compared with the predicted value of the grating vectors from contributing beam pair. The results show that it is possible to record square and rectangular photonic crystal structures using multiple beam holography.

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1. Introduction

Holography is a technique developed by Dennis Gabor in 1949 for recording the information contained in a wave scattered by an object by recording the interference pattern of the original wave front scattered by the object and a reference beam onto a photosensitive material. The interference pattern formed will be a series of bright and dark fringes. When the recorded hologram is illuminated with the reference beam, the original object wavefront is reproduced (Hutley, 1982).

The interference between two coherent collimated laser beams will result in an interference pattern with a periodicity in one dimension. As the number of beams is increased additional periodicities come into play. The interference of three coherent beams results in a 2-Dimensional periodic lattice pattern. The size and shape of the unit cells can be controlled by varying the angles between the beams. All five 2-dimensional Bravais lattices can be produced using this method as shown in (Escuti, 2004).

In this project, square and rectangular photonic crystal lattices with tuneable size were produced using a 3-beam holographic set up.

Possible applications of this method include use as biosensors where currently quantitative analysis of the number of bacteria in a sample is time consuming as they must be counted by eye (Cappucino, 2014), holographic beam splitters, band gap devices and holographic sensors.

2. Theoretical Background

Lasers produce beams with very low dispersion at a very narrow range of frequencies (Silfast, 2004). The electromagnetic waves emitted by lasers can be represented as plane waves. The amplitude of the electric field of the wave at time t and position x is given by the wave equation:

$$E_x = E_0 \sin(\omega t - kx) \quad (1)$$

Where E_0 is the maximum amplitude of the electric field, ω is the angular frequency and k is the wave vector (Giancoli, 1998)

2.1 Interference of two plane waves

The intensity, I , at any point, \mathbf{r} , which results from the interference of two coherent plane waves with wavevectors k_1 and k_2 and parallel polarisations is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I &= \langle [E_1 \cos(k_1 \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t) + E_2 \cos(k_2 \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t)]^2 \rangle \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} E_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} E_2^2 + \langle 2E_1 E_2 \cos(k_1 \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t) \cos(k_2 \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t) \rangle \\
 &= I_1 + I_2 + 2\sqrt{I_1 I_2} \cos(G \cdot \mathbf{r}) \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $G = k_1 - k_2$ is the difference wave vector and is defined as

$$G = \frac{2\pi}{\Lambda} \quad (3)$$

Where Λ is the period of the fringe pattern, G is normal to the fringes as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1- Diagram of two interfering plane waves.

This interference pattern is seen as a series of light and dark fringes corresponding with the areas of maximum and minimum intensity (Toal 2012, p. 50).

The distance between the fringes can be calculated from the rule of cosines and the relation between G and Λ .

$$G = \sqrt{k_1^2 + k_2^2 - 2k_1k_2 \cos \Psi} \quad (4.1)$$

As the magnitudes of the wavevectors are equal

$$G = \sqrt{2k^2(1 - \cos \Psi)} = 2 \frac{\pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{2(1 - \cos \Psi)} \quad (4.3)$$

Subbing in eqt 3 and knowing that $\sin^2 A = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \cos 2A)$

$$\Lambda = \frac{\lambda}{2 \sin \frac{\Psi}{2}} \quad (4.4)$$

The contrast of the fringes (Υ) is given by:

$$\Upsilon = \frac{2\sqrt{I_1 I_2}}{I_1 + I_2} \quad (5)$$

Υ is at a maximum when I_1 and I_2 are equal.

The waves which form an interference pattern must be derived from the same source to guarantee coherence (Pain, 2005).

2.2 Polarisation

The plane polarisation of an electromagnetic wave is defined as the orientation of oscillation of the electric field of the wave. The beams used in this project are all linearly polarised. Meaning the oscillation of the electric field is confined to a single plain (Toal, 2012).

If two coherent linearly polarised beams interfere in the manner shown in Figure 1 the variation in the intensity of the fringe pattern will be at a maximum when the polarisations are parallel.

If the angle between the planes of polarisation of the two beams is between $\frac{\pi}{2}$ and 0 the variation in intensity will be less than the parallel case as some of the light will not interfere. If the planes

of polarisation are perpendicular, there will be no variation of intensity in the fringes (Toal, 2014).

2.3 Diffraction

In the 17th century Francesco Grimaldi noted that when light was shone through a small hole in a screen, the resulting image on a wall opposite the screen was larger than the hole it came through. This phenomenon is known as diffraction and can be explained by Huygens principle which states that each point on a wave front can be considered as the source of a wavelet that spreads out in the forward direction. The new wave front is the tangent to all these wavelets (Giancoli,1998). Hutley states that '*A wave front is a locus of points at which the disturbance has the same phase*'

Figure 2 - A plane wave front with wavelets shown as dotted lines is diffracted through an aperture. The wavelets which form the part of the wave front which can pass through the aperture spread out in all forward directions. The blue arrow shows the direction of propagation of the wave front.

Figure 2 shows how Huygens principle can explain the phenomenon that Grimaldi had witnessed. The image projected on a screen from a single slit will form a series of fringes as a phase difference is introduced due to the difference in distances that waves from different parts of the slit must travel to reach the same point. Causing regions of destructive and constructive interference.

When two coherent waves from the same source overlap, the resulting wave amplitude will depend on the phase difference between the two waves in any particular point in space.

Consider eqt 1.

$$E_x = E_0 \sin(\omega t - kx) \quad (1)$$

And given that $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$ equation 1 becomes

$$E_0 \sin\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \quad (6)$$

The maximum amplitude of the waves will be same as they are both from the same wave front, they will leave the slits with equal phase for the same reason, and the time t will of course be the same for both waves. Therefore, the phase of the waves depends completely on the distance x travelled by the wave. When the difference between the distance travelled is $m\lambda + \frac{1}{2}\lambda$ the equation becomes

$$E_0 \sin\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (x + m\lambda + \frac{1}{2}\lambda)\right) = E_0 \sin\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} x + 2\pi + \pi\right) \quad (7)$$

Where $m\lambda$ is any whole number of wavelengths. As 2π is a full cycle, this means that there will be a phase difference of π between a wave that has travelled a distance x vs one that has travelled $x + m\lambda + \frac{1}{2}\lambda$. Since $\sin(x + \pi) = -\sin x$, the two waves will have opposite signs and their amplitudes will completely cancel. This is known as destructive interference. When the path difference is $m\lambda$, both waves will have exactly the same phase and their amplitudes will double. This is known as constructive interference.

When more slits are added the waves from each slit interfere with each other. In the case of two slits, when the distance between each slit and the screen upon which they are being projected is equal or different by $m\lambda$, the waves are perfectly in phase and they will interfere constructively but when one wave travels a distance of $\frac{1}{2}\lambda$ farther, destructive interference will

occur and the waves will cancel. Constructive interference will again occur when one wave travels one wavelength farther and so on. This will form a series of bright and dark fringes on the screen corresponding to the areas of constructive and destructive interference respectively. Figure 3 shows that the extra distance travelled by the second wave is equal to $d \sin \theta$ so when this distance is equal to a whole number multiple of the wavelength, constructive interference will occur. Therefore, the condition for constructive interference is (Giancoli,1998)

$$d \sin \theta = m\lambda \quad (8)$$

Figure 3 - Waves from two slits interfere at a point on a screen a distance of L away. The length of $d \sin \theta$ determines the phase difference between the waves and hence the intensity at that point.

The condition for constructive interference remains the same as the number of slits is increased but the maxima will become much sharper as a slight deviation from the maxima will result in destructive interference. The effect of the single slit diffraction is still present however, so the diffraction pattern due to the grating is contained within an envelope of the single slit pattern. Gratings which block some of the incident light and allow the rest to propagate through slits are known as amplitude gratings. Gratings can also have a varying refractive index which

causes a change in the optical path length of the material and thereby induces a phase difference in light traveling through different parts of the material. These are known as phase gratings.

Diffraction gratings can be characterised by their diffraction efficiency η :

$$\eta = \frac{I_{\text{Diffracted}}}{I_{\text{probe}}} \quad (9)$$

Where $I_{\text{Diffracted}}$ is the intensity of the diffracted light and I_{probe} is the intensity of the beam incident on the grating.

2.4 Fabrication of Holographic diffraction gratings

In 1927 Albert A. Michelson proposed that a grating could be produced by photographing interference fringes but at the time neither a light source nor recording materials were available to allow the idea to be realised. In the 1950s a team at the National Physical Laboratory managed to produce a grating by recording fringes on photographic plates (Hutley, 1982). The recordings require a ‘light sensitive’ material in which changes will be induced upon exposure to electromagnetic radiation. There are many materials which fulfil this requirement. The focus of this project is on holographic photopolymers (Calixto, 2017)

2.5 Holographic Recording in Photopolymers

The basic elements of any holographic photopolymer recording system are, a polymerizable monomer or monomers and a photoinitiator system. The photoinitiator system generally consists of a photosensitive dye and an electron donor. When the dye absorbs a photon of the appropriate wavelength, it reacts with the electron donor to produce free radicals which react with the monomer to begin a process of free radical chain polymerisation (Naydenova, 2004). The polymer chains are terminated when two free radicals interact (Naydenova, 2004). The polymerisation of the monomers in the bright fringes leads to a concentration gradient of the

monomers which causes the monomers to diffuse from the dark to bright fringes resulting in an increase in refractive index. Thus, in addition to the density change caused by the polymerisation process the concentration gradient driven diffusion from dark to bright fringes leads to modulation of the refractive index after holographic recording. The refractive index in the illuminated areas is different (typically higher) than the refractive index in the dark areas.

2.6 Formation of 2-Dimensional photonic lattices

The interference of two plane waves produces a pattern which varies in one dimension. Three beams are required to produce variations in two dimensions as the interference of three beams will produce three difference vectors, one for each pair of beams, which will all be in the same plane (Escuti, 2004). The 3-dimensional coordinate system used in this project comes from Escuti et al.

The directions of the wave vectors of each beam are defined as in Figure 4. ϕ_n is the angle of the beam with wavevector k_n from the x-axis in the xy-plane and θ_n is the angle the beam makes with the z-axis.

Figure 4 - Three beams interfering to form a two-dimensional grating recorded into a photopolymer material to fabricate a grating

The coordinate system is defined so that θ is the same for each beam and so that one of the grating vectors is parallel to the y-axis. This results in the grating vectors lying completely in the xy-plane. It can be seen from Figure 4 that by varying θ one will scale the magnitudes of all three grating vectors equally while varying ϕ will change the ratio between each of the grating vectors. The point of maximum intensity in the interference pattern will form a 2-dimensional lattice in the xy-plane with lattice constants given by:

$$a = \frac{\lambda}{|\sin \theta (\cos \Phi_1 - \cos \Phi_2)|} \quad (10)$$

$$b = \frac{\lambda}{2|\sin \theta \sin \Phi_2 \sin((\Phi_1 - \Phi_2)/2)|} \quad (11)$$

The angle γ between a and b is then:

$$\gamma = \frac{\Phi_1 + \Phi_2}{2} \quad (12)$$

The propagation angles required for any desired lattice constants and known wavelengths are:

$$\Phi_2 = \tan^{-1} \frac{\sin \gamma}{\cos \gamma - b/a} \quad (13)$$

$$\Phi_1 = 2\gamma - \Phi_2 \quad (14)$$

$$\Phi_3 = -\Phi_2 \quad (15)$$

$$\theta = \sin^{-1} \frac{\lambda/b}{2 \sin \Phi_2 \sin \gamma} \quad (16)$$

Escuti et al. show that all five 2-dimensional Bravais lattices can be constructed from these parameters.

Taking The Spatial Fourier Transform of a crystal lattice gives the reciprocal lattice. The reciprocal lattice vectors are equal to the grating vectors of the interference fringes.

2.7 Rectangular lattice

The requirement for the construction of a lattice where $\gamma = \pi/2$ is that ϕ_1 and ϕ_3 are π radians apart¹. This simplifies the mathematics in the theory section as the lattice constants now only need to be defined by two angles; θ and a new angle, α , defined as $\phi_2 - \phi_1$ or the angle that the second beam makes with the axis that the others two lie upon. The ratio between the lattice constants now relies solely on α .

¹ Due to the geometrical principal that the angle subtended by the points where a chord intersects a circle and the centre of that circle is twice that subtended at the circumference so if the Chord is a diameter then the angle subtended at the circumference is $\pi/2$ ”(Fenn 2001,p82).

Figure 5- The components of the three wave vectors in the xy plane and the three grating vectors resulting from their interference.

Consider Figure 5, the magnitude of the grating vectors can be calculated by using Pythagoras theorem. Let F equal the distance along G_{13} in the direction of k_1 from h and ρ equal the distance along G_{31} in the direction of k_2 from h so that

$$F = r(1 - \cos \alpha), \quad (17)$$

$$\rho = r(1 + \cos \alpha), \quad (18)$$

$$G_{12} = \sqrt{F^2 + h^2} \quad (19)$$

and

$$G_{23} = \sqrt{\rho^2 + h^2} \quad (20)$$

Expanding eqt 19 gives

$$G_{12} = \sqrt{r^2(1 - 2 \cos \alpha + \cos^2 \alpha + \sin^2 \alpha)} \quad (21)$$

Since $\cos^2 \alpha + \sin^2 \alpha = 1$

$$G_{12} = r\sqrt{2(1 - \cos \alpha)} \quad (22)$$

r is equal to the magnitude of the component of the wavevectors in the xy plane:

$$r = k_{xy} = k \sin \theta = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin \theta \quad (23)$$

And from eqt. 3 we know that $G = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$

Substituting eqts. 23 and 3 into eqt 22 gives

$$\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin \theta \sqrt{2(1 - \cos \alpha)} \quad (24)$$

So

$$A_{12} = \lambda / \sin \theta \sqrt{2(1 - \cos \alpha)} \quad (25)$$

Following similar logic

$$A_{23} = \lambda / \sin \theta \sqrt{2(1 + \cos \alpha)} \quad (26)$$

3. Methods and Materials

3.1 Design and construction of 3-beam set up

The set up was constructed in accordance with the principles described in section 2.7. The mirrors m_1 and m_3 were positioned so that there was an angle of 40° between beams 1 and 3 making $\theta = 20^\circ$. α can be varied by moving the mirror m_2 along the circumference of a semi-circle.

Figure 6 – schematic of set-up showing the relationship between all the variables used in constructing the apparatus. Each beam is assigned a colour for ease of understanding.

The plane of the semi-circle must intersect with beams 1 and 3 so that its base $|m_2|$ forms an isosceles triangle with the two other beams. The radius r will therefore be half of $|m_2|$. For practical reasons it is useful to define the lines h and F the vertical and horizontal distances of m_2 from the point where $|m_2|$ intersects with beam 1.

Figure 7 - Diagram of recording Set up. The colours of the beams are different for ease of understanding and to match with Figure 6. They do not represent the wavelength used for recording. List of elements: 1 - Cobalt 660nm laser, 2 - Electronically controlled shutter, 3 - spatial filter, 4 & 7 – adjustable apertures, 5 - collimating lens, 6 - adjustable half wave plate, 8 - polarising beam splitter (m_1), 9 - 50/50 beam splitter, 10- neutral density filter, 11,15 & 17- polarisers, 12 - photopolymer sample, 13 - power meter, 14 & 16 – mirrors (m_3 & m_2)

As stated in section 2.1 the grating G_{13} should be eliminated to form an even intensity profile. This was achieved by adjusting the polarisation of each beam. The beam splitter labelled 8 in Figure 7 is a polarising beam splitter. The light transmitted through the beam splitter is horizontally polarised while the light reflected towards m_3 (labelled 14 in Figure7) is vertically polarised so that there will be no intensity varying interference pattern produced by the superposition between beams 1 and 3. The adjustable half waveplate (6) can be rotated to adjust the ratio of the intensities of the reflected and transmitted beams. Another polariser (17) was placed along beam 2 (cyan) and adjusted so that beam 2 is polarised at 45° to beams 1 and 3.

The polarisers labelled 11 and 15 are in place to ensure that the beams 1 and 3 are completely linearly polarised.

Figure 8- Alignment of the electric fields of each beam. Again, the colours correspond to the same beams as in the previous figures.

The intensity of each beam was adjusted by rotating the polarisation of the light entering the polarising beam splitter using the variable half wave plate and by adding a neutral density filter to beam 1 so that the intensity of each beam was equal.

3.2 Modelling of square and rectangular Photonic crystal lattices

The rectangular lattice patterns formed when ϕ_1 and ϕ_3 are π radians apart were simulated on MATLAB by superimposing the three gratings shown in Figure 4. α can be varied in the programme and the resulting intensity profile is displayed.

The grating patterns for G_{12} and G_{23} were formed by first finding the angle δ of the grating vectors to the x axis

$$\delta_{G12} = \tan^{-1} \frac{\sin \alpha \sin(\pi/2 - \theta)}{1 - \cos \alpha} \quad (27)$$

δ_{G23} is then $\delta_{G12} + \pi/2$. The spatial periods of each grating were calculated using equations 22 and 23. The value of λ was set as unity so the simulation shows the relationship between the values of intensity within the xy plane but does not have a scale. The intensity at each point was calculated using

$$I(x, y) = \sin(GD) \quad (28)$$

Where G is the Grating vector and D is the distance from the top right (for G_{12}) and top left (for G_{23}) corners of the image. The intensity distribution for G_{13} was calculated using the same method except D was replaced with the x coordinate as the vector runs horizontally across the image and the spatial period was calculated using eq. 4.3.

3.3 Producing a rectangular lattice

To record a rectangular lattice α was set to $120^\circ \pm 3^\circ$ Which makes $\Lambda_{12} = 1.1\mu\text{m}$ (897 l/mm) and $\Lambda_{23} = 1.9\mu\text{m}$ (518 l/mm). Two sets of intensities were used for the recordings. They are shown in the table below:

	Intensity 1 (mW/cm ²)	Intensity 2 (mW/cm ²)
Beam 1	1.51±0.1	1.295±0.1
Beam 2	1.28±0.1	1.119±0.1
Beam 3	1.42±0.1	1.301±0.1
Total	4.21 ±0.4	3.715±0.4

Table 1- Intensity of light in each beam and the total intensity of each of the recording intensities

The exposure time for intensity set 1 ranged from 40-120s in steps of 20s and the exposure time for intensity set 2 was adjusted so that the total energy dosage incident on the polymer was the same for both sets of recordings. The exposure times were controlled by an electronic shutter, so the error is negligible.

Exposure time for intensity set 1 (s)	Exposure time for intensity set 2 (s)	Total energy per unit area (mJ/cm ²)
40	45	168 ±4
60	68	252 ±6
80	90	336 ±8
100	113	420 ±10
120	136	504 ±10

Table2- Exposure times for each of the two recording intensity sets and the total energy dosage incident on the photopolymer per unit area.

Once the recording was completed, the gratings were probed by a single beam and the intensities of the diffracted beams were measured. The percentage of the probe beam diffracted in each direction was calculated.

Four beams were visible after the gratings. They were labelled 1-4 as shown in Figure 9:

Figure 9- Numbering system used to label the beams. Beam 1 and 3 are caused by diffraction from grating₁₂ and grating₂₃ respectively, beam 2 is light diffracted from beams 1 and 3 by both gratings and beam 4 is the un-diffracted light from the probe beam.

The diffraction efficiency of each beam was calculated as follows

$$\eta_{b1} = \frac{I_{b1}}{I_{probe}} \quad (29)$$

$$\eta_{b2} = \frac{I_{b2}}{I_{probe}} \quad (30)$$

$$\eta_{b3} = \frac{I_{b3}}{I_{probe}} \quad (31)$$

Where I_{bn} is the intensity of beam n and I_{probe} is the intensity of the beam used to probe the grating.

The diffraction efficiency of each grating can be calculated as follows:

$$\eta_{12} = \eta_{b1} + \frac{\eta_{12}}{\eta_{12} + \eta_{23}} \times \eta_{b2} \quad (32)$$

Where η_{12} and η_{23} are the diffraction efficiency of G_{12} and G_{23} . The parameter $\frac{\eta_{12}}{\eta_{12} + \eta_{23}}$ is the ratio of the total diffracted light diffracted by G_{12} . Multiplying this ratio by η_{b2} gives the portion

of beam 2 that is due to G_{12} . η_{12} and η_{23} can be replaced with η_{b1} and η_{b2} as the light in each of these beams is due purely to each grating so that

$$\eta_{12} = \eta_{b1} + \frac{\eta_{b1}}{\eta_{b1} + \eta_{b3}} \times \eta_{b2} \quad (33)$$

By the same logic

$$\eta_{23} = \eta_{b3} + \frac{\eta_{b3}}{\eta_{b1} + \eta_{b3}} \times \eta_{b2} \quad (34)$$

Recordings were made of the interference pattern resulting from each beam pair using the same exposure times.

Square Lattices were recorded with a total intensity of 3.715 ± 0.4 mW/cm² as this intensity resulted in higher diffraction efficiencies, see Figure 15 and 17 The same exposure times as the rectangular lattice were used.

3.4 Preparation of photopolymer slides

The photopolymer used consisted of 1g Acrylamide (monomer), 0.2g N,N Methylene Bis-Acrylamide (cross linking monomer), 2ml of Triethanolamine (electron donor) and 3ml Methylene Blue (photosensitive dye) with a concentration of 1.1 mM in a matrix of 17.5ml of polyvinyl alcohol (binder) with a concentration of 10% wt/wt.

Figure 9- Pie chart of the proportion of each chemical component in the dry photopolymer layer.

3.5 Analysis of microscope images

Images of the gratings were taken post recording using a phase contrast microscope. The lattice parameters a , b and γ were measured from the image using ImageJ image processing software. The Fourier transform of the image was taken on ImageJ to get the Reciprocal lattice of the images. The reciprocal lattice vectors and the angle between them were measured.

4. Experimental results

4.1 Modelling of lattice pattern

The superposition of the 3 gratings was modelled on MATLAB. The resulting intensity profiles are shown below in Figure 10

Figure 10 - Simulation of the interference pattern for a rectangular lattice ($\alpha = 60^\circ$ & $\theta = 20^\circ$). Image a is the interference pattern from beams 1 and 2. b is the interference pattern from beams 2 and 3. The spatial period of grating₁₂ is larger than that in image b as G_{12} is smaller than G_{23} for $\alpha < 90^\circ$. The spatial period from G_{13} will always be the shortest as G_{13} is a diameter. Images d and e are the superposition of the three patterns viewed in xy plane and along the z axis respectively.

From Figure 10(d) we can see that the intensity profile of the 2-Dimensional lattice is indeed a rectangle but there is an extra unnecessary periodicity in the image as is clearly shown in Figure 10(e). This is due to G_{13} . If the effect of this grating is removed from the simulation, an even rectangular intensity profile is formed.

Figure 11- interference pattern of the 3 beams ($\alpha = 60^\circ$ & $\theta=20^\circ$) with the effects of grating¹³ removed image a is the pattern viewed along the z axis and image b is the pattern viewed along the xy plane.

The programme can simulate any 2-dimensional lattice pattern where $\gamma = 90^\circ$. Two of the five 2-dimensional Bravais lattices fall under this category; Rectangular and square. The intensity profile of a square lattice is shown below.

Figure 12- Simulation of the interference pattern of a square lattice ($\alpha = 90^\circ$ & $\theta=20^\circ$). The effects of grating²³ Have been removed from the pattern

Simulations of the predicted value of the lattice constants were also run using eqs. 25 and 26.

Figure13- (a) Predicted values of the lattice constants a (dashed blue line) and b (dotted red line) vs α for $\lambda = 660\text{nm}$ and $\theta = 20^\circ$. a and b converge at $\alpha = 90^\circ$. The ratio between a and b as α approaches 90° is inverted as α departs from 90° i.e. $\frac{a}{b}$ at $\alpha = 60^\circ = \frac{b}{a}$ at $\alpha = 120^\circ$ (b) The ratio of the lattice constants vs α from 10° - 90° .

4.2 Diffraction efficiencies

1-Dimensional diffraction gratings were recorded for each beam pair. The diffraction efficiency of the grating was measured post recording. No diffraction was observed from recordings of the interference of the -oppositely polarised- beams 1 and 3.

Vibration was an issue for the recordings of G_{23} . The first attempts at recording gratings with beams 2 and 3 were carried out during the afternoon and resulted in very low diffraction efficiencies. An example of one set of these recordings is displayed in table 3.

Exposure time (s)	Diffraction Efficiency (%)
40	$1.5 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-2}$
60	$6 \pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$
80	$1.6 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-2}$
100	$6 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-3}$
120	$5 \pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$

Table 3-Diffraction efficiency vs exposure time for the first attempt at recording a grating with beams 2 & 3. All recordings had far less than 1% diffraction efficiency.

This problem was not observed for grating₁₂. Another attempt was made at recording grating₂₃ during the evening when there was less vibrations in the building. This resulted in diffraction efficiencies orders of magnitude larger than the first attempt. The results are plotted in Figure14 alongside the results for G₁₂.

Figure 14 - Diffraction Efficiency of the gratings recorded by each beam pair vs exposure time at a total intensity of $2.79\text{mW}/\text{cm}^2$ for beams 1 & 2 and $2.70\text{mW}/\text{cm}^2$ for beams 2 & 3.

A gradual increase in the diffraction efficiency of the G₂₃ with exposure time is visible. The diffraction efficiency of G₁₂ is already at a maximum at 40s and decreases with further increase in exposure time.

Two-dimensional diffraction gratings were recorded with all three beams at an intensity of $4.21 \pm 0.4 \text{mW}/\text{cm}^2$. The diffraction efficiency for beam 1 was observed to be many times higher than beams 2 and three (Figure 15).

Figure 15- Diffraction Efficiency of each diffracted from the 3-beam grating vs exposure time at a total intensity of $4.21 \pm 0.4 \text{ mW/cm}^2$

The percentage of incident light diffracted by each grating was calculated from equations 33 and 34 and was plotted against exposure time in Figure 16. G_{12} has a far higher diffraction efficiency than G_{23} for this set of recordings.

Figure 16 - Diffraction efficiency of each grating vs exposure time for recordings with a total intensity of $4.21 \pm 0.4 \text{ mW/cm}^2$

Two-dimensional diffraction gratings were recorded with all three beams at an intensity of $3.715 \pm 0.4 \text{ mW/cm}^2$. The diffracted light is more easily shared between the diffracted beams at recordings of this intensity.

Figure 17 (a)-Diffraction efficiency of each diffracted beam vs exposure time at a total intensity of $3.715 \pm 0.4 \text{ mW/cm}^2$ (b)- The diffraction efficiency of the total light diffracted into all three beams vs exposure time.

Figure 18- Diffraction efficiency of each grating vs exposure time for recordings with a total intensity of $3.715 \pm 0.4 \text{ mW/cm}^2$

4.3 Analysis of Microscope Images

Phase contrast microscope images of the patterns recorded into the photopolymer were taken and the structures were analysed.

Figure 19 - Microscope image of a rectangular lattice pattern formed where $\alpha = 60^\circ$.

The distance between 22 of the fringes for each grating was measured 4 times. The measurements are shown in table 4:

$22\Lambda_{12}$ (pixels)	$22\Lambda_{23}$ (pixels)
491	305
493	304
494	302
497	303

Table 4- distance in pixels of 22 spatial periods of the rectangular lattice

$$22\Lambda_{12} = 494 \pm 3 \text{ pixels}$$

$$22\Lambda_{23} = 304 \pm 2 \text{ pixels}$$

So, the ratio r between the fringes is

$$r = \frac{494}{304} = 1.63$$

$$\Delta r = \sqrt{(3/494)^2 + (2/304)^2} \times 1.63 = 1 \times 10^{-2}$$

The predicted ratio for $\alpha = 120^\circ \pm 3^\circ$ can be calculated using equations 25 and 26

$$\frac{\Lambda_{12}}{\Lambda_{23}} = \sqrt{\frac{1 - \cos \alpha}{1 + \cos \alpha}} = 1.7 \pm 0.1$$

The measured result for r falls within the range predicted by the theory.

The angle γ between the lattice vectors is $90^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Figure 20 - Microscope image of lattice pattern formed where $\alpha = 90^\circ$.

The results of four measurements of each 22 fringe spacings were:

$22\Lambda_{12}$ (pixels)	$22\Lambda_{23}$ (pixels)
386	360
385	362
379	359
382	361

Table 5- distance in pixels of 22 spatial periods of the square lattice

The mean value of $22\Lambda_{23}$ is 360 ± 2 pixels and the mean value of $22\Lambda_{12}$ is 383 ± 4 pixels. This gives a ratio between the fringe spacing of.

$$r = \frac{\Lambda_{23}}{\Lambda_{12}} = 0.94 \pm 0.01$$

The predicted ratio for $\alpha = 90^\circ \pm 3^\circ$ is 1 ± 0.1

The value of r obtained by measuring the fringe spacings of the square lattice fall within the range predicted by the theory.

The angle Υ between the lattice vectors is $90^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

The Fourier Transforms of the microscope images of the lattice patterns were taken using ImageJ image processing software. The length of the grating vectors and the angle between them was measured.

The results of three measurements of the grating vectors of the Fourier transform of the rectangular grating are shown in Table 6:

G_{12} (pixels)	G_{23} (pixels)
732	1193
738	1204
733	1205

Table 6- Lengths of the grating vectors

The mean length of G_{12} is 734 ± 4 pixels and the mean value of G_{23} is 1201 ± 7

Figure 21-Fourier Transform of microscope image of rectangular grating

Thus, the ratio between the grating vectors is

$$r = \frac{G_{12}}{G_{23}} = \frac{734}{1201} = 0.61 \pm 4 \times 10^{-3}$$

The angle between the grating vectors is $90^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$

The results of three measurements of the grating vectors of the Fourier transform of the square grating are shown in Table 7

G_{12}	G_{23}
946	1007
947	1004
949	1005

Table 7- Lengths of the grating vectors of the Fourier transform of a square grating measured on Image J

The mean length of G_{12} is 947 ± 2 pixels and the mean length of G_{23} is 1005 ± 2 pixels.

The ratio between the grating vectors is:

$$r = \frac{G_{12}}{G_{23}} = \frac{947}{1005} = 0.94 \pm 3 \times 10^{-3}$$

Figure 22-Fourier Transform of microscope image of square grating

5. Discussion

Two 2-dimensional lattice patterns were recorded onto photopolymer layers in this project using a 3-beam holographic set up at two intensity sets and five exposure times.

The total diffraction efficiency of the structures was higher, and the diffracted light was more evenly distributed between the beams for the gratings recorded at the lower intensity. It is difficult to tell whether this result is due to the variation in intensity or due to vibrations during the recording.

Vibration was a major issue in this experiment, particularly for the gratings formed between beams 2 and 3. A possible reason for this is that the mirror m_2 was placed at a larger height from the optical table than is usual so any vibrations at the level of the table are amplified for m_2 . The difference of path lengths between beam 2 and 3 is also much larger than that of beam 1 and 2. This would make the effect of vibrations more pronounced for G_{23} . This would be resolved by using a more stable mount for m_2 .

The intensities of the beams were not at the optimal levels for maximum fringe contrast, ie does not satisfy eq.5. Instead of ensuring that all three beams have equal intensity, it should be ensured that the x and y components of the electric fields of beam 2 should be equal the electric fields of beams 1 and 3 respectively. This is shown graphically in Figure 23.

Figure 23- The magnitude of the electric fields of each beam. It is clear that the magnitude of the electric field of beam 2 E_2 is less than the sum of the electric field of the other two beams.

As E_3 and E_1 are perpendicular the magnitude that E_2 should have can be calculated using Pythagoras equation.

$$E_2 = \sqrt{E_1^2 + E_3^2} \quad (34)$$

The magnitudes of E_1 and E_3 are equal so eqt* reduces to:

$$E_2 = \sqrt{2}E_1 = \sqrt{2}E_3 \quad (35)$$

6. Conclusions and future work

The aim of this project was to produce periodical crystal lattice patterns of tuneable size in photopolymer layers. This was achieved for lattices where $\Upsilon = 90^\circ$ (rectangular and square lattices).

The experimentally measured ratios between the lattice vectors for the square and rectangular lattices ($\alpha=120^\circ$) 0.94 ± 0.003 and 0.61 ± 0.004 respectively are in good agreement with the ratios predicted by the models for the angle α , 1 ± 0.1 for the square grating and 0.58 ± 0.1 for the rectangular grating and The angle Υ between the lattice vectors was measured to be $90^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ for both lattice patterns. This figure is in agreement with the predicted value of 90° .

Introducing an angle of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ between the polarisation states of beams 1 and 2 successfully eliminated the effects of G_{13} on the lattice pattern.

Future work

Any of the five 2-dimensional Bravais lattices could be recorded using the same set-up by moving m_2 along the z axis as well as in the xy plane. A short qualitative description of how this might be achieved is included in the appendix.

The set-up described in this project could be used to record 2-dimensional lattice patterns onto a photopolymer composition similar to that used by (Pavani et al, 2006) to produce surface relief gratings (SRGs) for use as biosensors. The unit cells of the lattice patterns could be tuned to fit exactly one bacteria cell of a certain species. It is envisaged that the liquid samples containing the bacteria are poured onto the grating so that each bacterium occupies one unit cell, when the optimum surface relief structure is utilised. The hypothesis is that the presence of the bacteria would modulate the diffraction efficiency and from the measurement of the diffraction efficiency change the number of bacteria in the sample could be quantitatively characterised.

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Appendix

Production of all five Bravais lattices

Moving m_2 in the positive z direction is equivalent to moving it in the positive y direction from the perspective of the interference grating as shown in Figure a:

Figure a - Effect of moving m_2 in the positive z direction viewed in the yz plane

The addition of Δy to h from the perspective of the grating causes an increase in θ . The change when viewed in the xy plane is as follows:

Figure b - Effect of moving m_2 in the positive z direction viewed in the xy plane. The colour coding of the arrows is the same as in the report. The increase in θ causes the diameter of the circle to grow. The coordinate system moves in the positive y direction (equivalent to tilting the sample) to ensure that the condition that θ is equal for all beams is met.

In Figure b, The position of beams 1 and 3 (tips of the red and purple arrows) doesn't change but the angle between the three beams does. Therefore, all five of the two-dimensional Bravais lattices can be produced by moving m_2 and by tilting the sample.

MATLAB code used to simulate the interference patterns

```
%%3-beam interference simulation
```

```
%This programme models the square and rectangular lattice patterns that  
%form due to the interference of three laser beams
```

```

%initialise arrays
grating12 = zeros(1000);
grating23 = grating12;
grating13 = grating12;

theata = pi()/9; % angle between each beam and the z axis
alpha = pi()/3; %angle between beams 1 & 2

%% interference pattern between beam 1 & 2

GratingAngle12 = atan(sin(alpha)*sin((pi()/2)-theata)/(1-cos(alpha)));
%anlge of the grating vector to the x axis

d12 = 1/(sin(theata)*sqrt(2*(1-cos(alpha)))); % fringe spacing of the
grating
G12 = 2*pi()/d12; % magnitude of the grating vector

% construct a line perpendicular to the wave where the corner of the square
% is on the line

m12 = tan(GratingAngle12); %slope
C12 = 1-m12; % intercept

% the standing wave that is grating 12 is created by calculating the
% intensity of each point in the image based on its distance from the line
% perpendicular to grating 12 which intersects the grating vector at the
% corner or the image.

for i = 1:1:length(grating12)
    for j = 1:1:length(grating12)

        D = abs(m12*i + j + C12)/sqrt(m12^2 + 1); % distance from point to
the constructed line

        grating12(j,i) = sin(G12*D/80); %save the amplitudes of the grating
st each pointinto a two dimensional array
    end
end

%display the intensity distribution
figure(1)
imagesc(grating12)
axis off

%%interference between beams 2 and 3
%the intensity distribution of G23 is calculated and displayed using the
%same method as grating two one expept that it is perpendicular to g2 and
%the spacing is different due to alpha

gratingAngle23 = atan((2-(1-cos(alpha)))/sin(alpha)*sin((pi()/2)-
theata))+pi()/2;
%d23 = sqrt((2-(1-cos(alpha)))^2 + (sin(alpha)*sin((pi()/2)-theata))^2)/2;
d23 = 1/(sin(theata)*sqrt(2*(1+cos(alpha))));
G23 = 2*pi()/d23;

```

```

m23 = tan(gratingAngle23);
C23 = 1 - 1000*m23;

for i = 1:1:length(grating23)
    for j = 1:1:length(grating23)

        D = abs(m23*i + j + C23)/sqrt(m23^2 + 1); % distance from point to
the constructed line

        grating23(j,i) = sin(G23*D/80);
    end
end
figure(2)
imagesc(grating23)
axis off

%% interference between beams 1 and 3

% the fringe spacing for this grating can be obtained using the bragg
% equation.

d13 = 1/(2*sin(theata));
G13 = 2*pi()/d13;

% the grating runs horozonally to the image so the intensity at anypoint i
% only based on its horozontal coodinate

for i = 1:1:length(grating13)

    grating13(1:end,i) = 0*sin(G13*i/80); %the amplitude is multiplied by 0
to represent the cross polarisation of beam 1 and 3
end

figure(3)
imagesc(grating13)
axis off

finalPattern = (grating12 + grating13 + grating23)/3; % the final pattern
is the superposition of all three gratings

% display the lattice pattern. imagesc gives a flat image where the colour
% represents the intensity at that point ang mesh gives out a 'three
% dimensional' image where the intensity is represented by the colour and
% the height.

figure(4)
%mesh(finalPattern)
imagesc(finalPattern)
axis off

```